

LITERARY REVIEW OF VIDALAK IN NETRAROGA W.S.R. TO EYE DISORDERS

*¹Dr. Santosh Kumar Sahu, ²Dr. Ved Parkash, ³Dr. Payal Sharma

¹Assistant Professor Department of Shalaky Tantra, Government Ayurved College & Hospital, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Dravya Guna, Manglayatan Ayurvedic Medical College & Research Centre, Aligarh, UP.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Prasuti Tantra & Striog Vigyana, Manglayatan Ayurvedic Medical College & Research Centre, Aligarh, U.P.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Santosh Kumar Sahu

Assistant Professor, Department of Shalaky Tantra, Government Ayurved College & Hospital, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17481892>,

How to cite this Article: ¹Dr. Santosh Kumar Sahu, Dr. Ved Parkash, Dr. Payal Sharma. (2025). Assistant Professor Department of Shalaky Tantra, Government Ayurved College & Hospital, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 11(11), 30-32.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 01/10/2025

Article Revised on 21/10/2025

Article Published on 01/11/2025

ABSTRACT

Shalaky Tantra is one of the most essential branches of Ayurveda amongst 8 branches. It specifically deals with disorders of all urdhvajatrugata roga i.e. supraclavicular regions. Netra possess prime position as they are the gateway to the external world. Netra is mentioned as Pradhana Indriya and to protect it one should consider it as prime objective. Without the eyes the whole world appears black and one depends on others for the lifetime. There are 94 eye disorders mentioned in Ayurveda & from varying symptoms like minute itching in eyes upto complete loss of vision. From managing to treating Kriyakalpa is considered as choice of therapy in treatment of Netra Gata Rogas. Vidalaka is one of the Kriyakalpa procedure used in eye disorders.

KEYWORDS: Vidalaka, Netra Gata Roga, Sarva Netra Rogahara Vidalaka, eye disorders, ayurveda..

INTRODUCTION

“Sankshepathaha Kriyayogo Nidana Parivarjanam” – Ayurveda always focuses on the importance of nidana in the pathogenesis of any roga. This shloka clearly signifies that any roga can abolish from life if one avoids the causative factor completely. In roga pariksha, nidana holds on top which signifies its importance keeping rest behind i.e. nidana, purvarupa, rupa, upshaya, samprapti. Netra – Pradhan amongst all the 5 indriyas and it got prelevance importance by our acharyas because of its role. (Nayana Pradhanam). Utmost care is must needed for its normal physiological activities. Majority of world is suffering with eye disorder because of their negligence or unawareness regarding causative. And if left untreated it proceeds to life threatening complications.

Nidana mentioned by Acharya Sushruta are.^[1]

1. Ushnabitaptasyajalapravesath- Immersing in cold water immediately after getting exposed to heat/sun.

2. Doorekshanath (Looking at very distant objects regularly for a longer time).
3. Swapanaviparyaya (Abnormal sleeping habits) abnormal sleeping habits (Diva swapna/Nisi jagarana).
4. Prasakthasamrodhana (Continuous weeping for several days).
5. Kopa and Shoka (Excessive Anger and Grief).
6. Klesha (Stress Pain, Anguish, Trouble)
7. Abhighaatha (Trauma).
8. Atimaithuna (Excessive sex)
9. Shuktharaanalaamlanishevana (alcoholic beverages)
10. Kulatthamashanishevana (Excessive use of horse Gram and Black gram)
11. Vega vinigraha (Suppression of urges)
12. Atisweda (Excessive sudation to eye)
13. Dhoomanishevanath (Excessive exposure to smoke)
14. Chardhivighatath (Suppressing the urge of vomiting)

15. Vamanathiyogath (Excessive vama therapy)
Excessive vama therapy causes “Akshiorvyavruithi” (Protrusion of eye ball).
16. Bhashpagrahath (Suppressing tears during grief)
17. Sukshmanireekshanath(staring objects for longer duration)

Vidalak review- Kriya kalpa considered as best modality in Ayurvedic procedures in Shalaky tantra specially in netragata vyadhi. Acharya Sushruta has mentioned 5 kriya kalpa - Tarpana, putpaka, ashchyotan, anjana and seka.^[2]

Acharya Sharangdhara has mentioned two more in addition to above 5 i.e Vidalaka and Pindi.^[3] In kriya kalpa the mode of action is due to the local contact with disease of the drug. The local action is more effective than systemic because the tissue comes in direct contact over a period of time. According to Ayurveda- it is mentioned that Srotomaya Purusha- the whole body consist of Sukshma Srotasa. Through these pores or channels the minute particles penetrates in the skin. At this stage the Upshoshana Guna of Vata Dosha helps in the penetration and absorption of the drug.

Bhrajaka Pitta present in skin is responsible for metabolism of the drug applied over the skin. Vidalaka when mixed with Ghrita reaches into the deeper tissues of the eye as Ghrita is both hydrophilic and lipophilic in nature. Vidalaka mixed with Madhu can also reach the deeper tissue because of its Sukshma Guna and its Yogvahi property.

- efficacy of drug and their effect locally.
- These drugs cross blood aqueous barrier, blood vitreous barrier and blood retinal barrier and reach the target tissue
- The mechanical effect of these therapies reduces swelling and pain
- Local vasodilatation helps in reducing inflammation
- Increases the absorption of drug much faster than systemic drugs.

Method of application

Vidalaka is also called lepa or external application.

Preparation- In this, the churna form of drugs are collected dosha accordingly or according vyadhi and then is mixed with hot/cold water or kwath and a desired paste is made and applied around the eyes except eye lashes resembling cat's eye or vidalaka.^[4] Vidalak is said so because it resembles the appearance of cat's eye.

Time of administration- It is advised to do the procedure in day time but not at night, however in painful conditions it can be done even at night also.^[5] Acharya Charaka has described Vidalaka in netraroga with conditions like daha, lalima, shoth and srava. Acharya has divided netraroga in 4 types with respect to Dravya & Doshas.^[6]

Acharya Charaka mentions Drava sweda for aggravating the Pitta samsrta vyadhi which is indirectly called as Seka.^[7] Seka is denoted as an important kriya kalpa by acharya sushruta.^[8] Pariseka has been mentioned with aschyotana karma.^[9] Both the therapies are same except in

- par se use in disease condition
- Dose administration
- Time of usage

Dose: since, Vidalaka sub-type of Lepa Kalpana, which is considered as an initial Chikitsa of Vrana Shotha. The amount of Vidalaka is same as the dose of Mukha Lepa 1/4th of the thickness of thumb- Kanistha Matra 1/3rd of the thickness of the thumb- Madhyama Matra 1/2nd of the thickness of the thumb- Uttama Matra

It is removed before it gets dry because after drying it loses its property. After Vidalaka is applied following things are contraindicated like diwaswapa, ati atap sevan, ativaak, laugh, weeping etc.^[10] If these measures are not followed it will cause itching, dryness, Pinasa and dimness of vision.

S.NO.	Vidalakprakar	Drug used	Disease
1.	Bhumi amalkilepa	Saindhav, bhumyaamalki	Netra abhishyandi
2.	Kumari dadimalepa	Kumari, dadima	Sarva netraroga
3.	Darvyadi rasa kriya	Darvi, patol etc.	Daha, ashru, raga, ruja.
4.	Saindhav lodhraadilepa	Saindhav, lodhra	Netra ruja
5.	Arma nashakvidalak	Maricha, kesranjan etc.	Arma roga/pterygium
6.	Sarva netrarogaharavidalak	Yashtimadhu, gairaik etc.	Sarva netraroga
7.	Manashiladilepa	Manashila, tagar, ela	Anjana namika
8.	Chandanadividalak	Chandan, maricha,ela etc.	Vata abhishandajadhimantha
9.	Daruharidra. Tutha, haritki,		Pitta abhishandajadhimantha

DISCUSSION

Mode of action: It relies on- Route of administration- As Vidalaka is applied over twak/skin. It quickly penetrates in skin. Since epidermis layer acts as lipid barrier the solubility of the drug totally depends upon the lipid solubility of the contents used. The dermis is freely

permeable to many solutes. It is easy and fast absorbing thus showing good efficacy & results. Solubility and Bioavailability: Absorption of drug depends upon solubility and the site of application. In Vidalaka, the application time of the drug is more as compared to Ashchyotana and Seka. This increases the bioavailability.

More time drug stays in contact on site, more is the rate of absorption & better is the effect. Example - The drugs mixed in Vidalaka shows their own property like if prepared from Dashamoola will be Shothashamaka, if prepared from Chandan it will be dahashamaka.

CONCLUSION

Since, Vidalaka is an external application procedure it can be used easily. It is useful in acute eye conditions or in Amavastha of the Netra Rogas. It provide scalming effect to the eyes. If used for proper condition in appropriate amount and for proper time it gives tremendous results.

REFERENCES

1. Sushruta, Sushruta Samitha, Uttara tantra, aupadravikaadhyaya Susrutasamitha, Uttara sthana by Prof. K.R. Srikantamurthy, Varanasi: Chaukhambhaorientalia, 2012; 609: 1, 26-27.
2. Sushruta Samhita ayurveda tatvasandipika –Hindi commentary edited by Kaviraj Ambika Dutt Shastri, 18/4-93.
3. Sharangdhar Samhita Uttar Khand By Brahmanand Tripathi, 7/1,424.
4. Shalaky Tantra Kriya Kalpa Vigyan-Prof K.S Dhiman, 51.
5. K.P Srikanta Moorti, Astanga Sangrah Samhita by Acharya Vagbhatt, vol.1 edited by Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 6th edition. Sutrasthana 32/4.
6. Charak Samhita Chikitsa Sthana 26/231 Caraka Samhita of Agnivesha revised by Caraka and Dridhbala with introduction by Vaidya Samrata Sri Satya Narayan Sastri Padmabhushan with elaborated vidyotnihindicommentry part 2 by Chaukambha Bharti Academy Varanasi.
7. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, Chaukhamba publications, Delhi, edited by Vaidya yadavji Trikamji acharya, Chikitsa sthana 14th chapter, 2014; 77,738.
8. Sushrutha, Sushrutha Samhita, ChaukhambaSurbharatiprakashan, Delhi, edited by Vaidya yadavji Trikamji acharya, Uttara tantra chapter 18th chapter, 2014; 636: 824.
9. Shalaky Tantra Kriya Kalpa Vigyan –Prof K.S. Dhiman, 7.
10. K.P Srikanta Moorti, Astanga Sangrah Samhita by Acharya Vagbhatt vol.1 edited by Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 6 th edition. Sutrasthana 21/8.